
Using MCDA To Select Countermeasures Against Fake News

Journal:	<i>Journal of Information, Communication & Ethics in Society</i>
Manuscript ID	JICES-07-2024-0089.R1
Manuscript Type:	Journal Paper
Keywords:	MCDA, M-Macbeth, Risk Management, Fake News, Disinformation

SCHOLARONE™
Manuscripts

Using MCDA To Select Countermeasures Against Fake News

Abstract

The advent of fake news poses a significant threat to communities, organisations and individuals, contributing to the erosion of public trust in institutions and democracy. This is aggravated should we consider the multiplicity of fake news and, thus, the multitude of risk and their impact on society. This research proposes tackling fake news as a digital risk by applying a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) to select the appropriate countermeasures for law enforcement agencies (LEAs) to tackle high stakes crime associated with fake news. Here, we demonstrate the applicability of MCDA through a systematic approach using M-Macbeth to present alternatives for mitigating high-impact instances of crime in a community and measure the attractiveness of each alternative. Results indicate that to mitigate risk effectively, prioritising risk using adequate strategies and appropriate courses of action is crucial. Nevertheless, the contributions of this research work allowed us to comprehend the best alternative to mitigate the risk of fake news and provide a realistic approach to support LEAs in decision analysis.

Key Words: MCDA, M-Macbeth, Risk Management, Fake News, Disinformation

1. Introduction

Fake news (FN) is not just a term but a pressing issue that demands our immediate attention. It refers to the widespread dissemination of false or misleading information, intentionally or unintentionally. This urgent phenomenon poses a significant risk as it can manipulate public perception and influence societal dynamics. FN is closely related to two key terms—disinformation and misinformation—which are often used interchangeably but represent distinct concepts that are important to differentiate [1].

Disinformation refers to the deliberate creation and spread of falsehoods, usually driven by motives such as political, financial, or ideological gain [2]. It is a calculated effort to deceive and mislead, as recognised by institutions such as the European Union and the British Parliament, which acknowledge disinformation as a fundamental problem in modern society [3], [4], [5]. On the other hand, misinformation occurs when individuals unknowingly share inaccurate information, believing it to be true. While disinformation is intentional, misinformation is accidental. However, both contribute to the erosion of public trust, social division, and significant risks, especially in the digital age where fake news rapidly circulates on social media platforms [2].

The issue of FNs is not modern—it has existed throughout history in various forms, from the propaganda tactics of ancient Rome to the press manipulation during World War II [6], [7]. More recently, the ongoing conflict between Ukraine and Russia has demonstrated how false information plays a pivotal role in the strategies of modern warfare. This historical context underscores the gravity of the issue. The difference today lies in the advancement of technology, particularly the rise of social media, which acts as a catalyst, allowing FNs to spread swiftly and more widely, exacerbating its threat to organisations, individuals, and society [7].

This paper explores the intersection of fake news as a threat and established risk management principles, particularly those outlined in the ISO 31XXX family of standards [8]. By examining risk management strategies, the paper proposes a method for mitigating the digital risks of FNs using Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA). This approach enables decision-makers to rank potential countermeasures and identify effective strategies to combat the high-impact crime of disinformation within a community.

1
2
3 **Traditionally, risk management strategies have been applied to address financial, operational,**
4 **or strategic uncertainties, including those arising from the spread of FNs. A fundamental**
5 **principle of risk management is that anything of value is worth protecting [8]. While this**
6 **principle is often applied in organisational contexts, it is equally essential to safeguard our**
7 **communities from the multifaceted risks of FNs. Effective strategies must be adopted to prevent**
8 **the mismanagement of high-impact threats.**

9
10
11
12
13
14 **Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) across the European Union are not just tasked with**
15 **investigating crimes related to FNs but with proactively managing and preventing them. They**
16 **must act quickly when faced with high-stakes situations. This paper strongly advocates for a**
17 **proactive approach to managing disinformation risks, which have been identified as both severe**
18 **and highly likely to occur in specific communities. By providing LEAs with a structured method**
19 **for responding to such risks, this work offers a framework to support more effective decision-**
20 **making and mitigate the negative consequences of fake news.**

21
22
23
24
25
26
27 **The structure of this paper is as follows: The next section presents a research background on**
28 **risk management, MCDA, and the intersection of these two subjects. A detailed explanation of**
29 **the design science research methodology follows this. The fourth section introduces the author's**
30 **proposal, followed by a demonstration and evaluation of the findings. Finally, the paper**
31 **concludes with a summary of the key insights, a discussion of the research limitations, and**
32 **suggestions for future work.**

33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40 **2. Research Background**

41
42
43 This section delves into Risk Management, Fake News, and MCDA. This segment encapsulates a
44 comprehensive exploration of these key topics, providing the foundation for understanding our
45 research's intricacies and interconnections.

46 47 48 49 **2.1 Risk Management**

50
51 **In today's increasingly uncertain world, it is essential to adopt effective strategies that help**
52 **organisations and communities anticipate potential risks and mitigate their impact through**
53 **appropriate countermeasures. One of the most widely recognised frameworks for managing**
54 **risk is the ISO 31000 standard, which provides guidelines and principles to address risks**
55 **systematically and effectively [8]. The standard offers a structured framework that can be**
56 **adopted by organisations, governments, and other entities to implement policies, procedures,**
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 and practices designed to manage risks comprehensively. These activities include
4 communicating and consulting with stakeholders, setting the context, and continuously
5 assessing, treating, monitoring, and reporting on risks [8].
6
7

8
9 The ISO 31000 risk management process consists of several vital steps. First, it emphasises the
10 importance of *communication and consulting* to ensure that all relevant parties are informed
11 and involved in risk management decisions. Next, the *scope, context, and criteria* for risk
12 assessment are established to define the boundaries and objectives of the risk management
13 process. Following this, a thorough *risk assessment* is conducted, which includes identifying,
14 analysing, and evaluating risks. Once risks are assessed, the next step is *risk treatment*, where
15 appropriate measures are taken to mitigate or manage the risks. The framework also highlights
16 the importance of *monitoring and reviewing* the effectiveness of risk management actions
17 and *recording and reporting* to ensure transparency and accountability throughout the process
18 [8].
19
20
21
22
23
24
25

26
27 In addition to the ISO 31000 guidelines, alternative approaches to risk management are being
28 proposed to meet the evolving challenges of the modern world. For example, Chapter 5 of
29 Corporate Risk Management advocates for rethinking traditional risk management practices,
30 arguing that risk management should be about avoiding losses and creating value for businesses
31 [9]. This perspective shifts the focus from a defensive approach to one that sees risk
32 management as an opportunity for strategic growth and value creation.
33
34
35
36
37

38
39 As we delve deeper into the nature of risk, it is crucial to understand that the digital landscape
40 presents its own set of challenges. In the next section, the paper will explore the digital risks
41 posed by FNs, summarising their nature and impact better to contextualise the threat within
42 modern risk management strategies.
43
44
45
46
47

48 2.2 Fake News

49
50 The term *Fake News* (FN) is often associated with a wide range of terminology, making it
51 somewhat challenging to differentiate between similar concepts. Terms such as disinformation,
52 misinformation, false information, fabricated information, and partisan information are
53 frequently used in connection with FN, each with its nuanced meaning [10]. A standard
54 definition of FN is the intentional or unintentional spread of false or misleading information in
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 **the public sphere, with the potential to cause harm to organisations, individuals, public**
4 **institutions, and the media [7].**
5
6

7 **FN spreads effectively in the modern era, largely due to the proliferation of online platforms,**
8 **with social media being a key player in its dissemination [1]. State or private actors often exploit**
9 **these platforms to spread FNs, employing sophisticated techniques to propagate falsehoods.**
10 **These methods can include using automated bots that rapidly disseminate false information**
11 **across networks or infiltrating real social media accounts to lend credibility to FNs [11]. While**
12 **FN is often associated with social media, it is important to note that its reach extends beyond**
13 **digital platforms. Fake news can also be found in traditional media forms, such as newspapers,**
14 **newscasts, and other periodicals, demonstrating that false information can take many forms**
15 **and use various channels for dissemination [12].**
16
17

18 **Understanding the intent behind the spread of FN is crucial in distinguishing between**
19 **disinformation and misinformation. If the spread of false information is a deliberate act**
20 **intended to mislead, it is classified as disinformation. On the other hand, if the spread results**
21 **from an error or mistake, it is considered misinformation [2]. Misinformation can also include**
22 **incomplete information that leads to misunderstandings [7]. Literature suggests that private**
23 **interests, often seeking political or financial gain, target vulnerable individuals to act as**
24 **unwitting participants in the further spread of FN [13].**
25
26

27 **Malicious actors typically employ three common strategies when targeting organisations with**
28 **fake news:**
29
30

- 31 **1. They spread false information to achieve financial gain or to discredit and manipulate**
32 **political discourse.**
- 33 **2. They often label their distorted version of reality as the only factual source of**
34 **information, deliberately misleading audiences.**
- 35 **3. In a more insidious tactic, they accuse legitimate news outlets of spreading fake news [7].**
36
37

38 **Understanding the behaviour and motivations of these perpetrators is crucial for assessing the**
39 **risks associated with FN and developing strategies to counter its harmful effects.**
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

2.3 Multi-criteria Decision Analysis

Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA), also known as Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM), is a decision-support technique designed to assist in complex decision-making processes that involve multiple criteria. These criteria can often be conflicting, making decision-making challenging. MCDA offers a structured and systematic approach to simultaneously evaluate various factors, improving the overall quality of decisions [14], [15], [16]. It is widely used in healthcare, education, and public policy, where decisions must account for diverse and sometimes competing interests. The strength of MCDA lies in its ability to evaluate and rank alternative options based on the importance of different criteria and how well the alternatives perform relative to these criteria, all while considering multiple stakeholder perspectives [17].

Two critical steps are necessary to make effective decisions using MCDA. First, the problem must be clearly and comprehensively defined, along with its limitations or constraints. Second, it is essential to establish the roles of the key participants in the decision-making process. The Decision-Maker (DM), whether a CEO, doctor, manager, judge, or consumer, is ultimately responsible for making the final decision. The Decision Analyst (DA) systematically evaluates alternatives and provides a structured framework to rank these options. This framework is crucial for guiding the DM toward informed choices.

The role of the DA is to build a detailed decision model that accurately reflects the problem at hand. This model ensures that the evaluation process is rigorous and considers all relevant factors. MCDA is an essential tool in this process, offering a structured approach for assessing and prioritising options in situations where multiple criteria are involved, and consensus is required.

It is important to note that MCDA does not dictate decisions; rather, it supports the decision-making process by providing a clear and logical structure for evaluating options. Every decision, whether consciously or not, involves balancing multiple factors. MCDA helps make this balancing process explicit and more manageable, ensuring the objectivity and fairness of the decision-making process [14].

A common approach within MCDA is using a hierarchical value tree, which structures the decision problem by breaking it down into smaller, more manageable components. This value tree helps assess the value function, representing the DM's preferences. The preferences in the decision process must follow the principle of preferential independence, ensuring consistency

1
2
3 **in evaluating options. Another critical aspect of MCDA is elicitation procedures, which involve**
4 **gathering insights directly from decision-makers [14]. These procedures ensure that the**
5 **decision process is collaborative, aligning with the real-world preferences and needs of the**
6 **stakeholders involved.**
7
8
9

10
11 **In summary, MCDA provides a robust framework for addressing complex decision-making**
12 **scenarios by evaluating multiple criteria, considering stakeholder perspectives, and supporting**
13 **decision-makers in making informed, well-structured choices.**
14
15
16

17 **3. Research Methodology**

18
19
20 This section outlines the methodology employed, emphasising the utilisation of Design Science
21 Research (DSR).
22
23

24 **3.1. Design Science Research**

25
26 The proposed methodology – Design Science Research – aims to create innovative and practical
27 solutions to solve complex problems. This objective is achieved through the design of an artefact and
28 its consequent demonstration and evaluation. This research follows the guidelines for correctly
29 implementing DSR in Information Systems [18]. These guidelines encompass the following
30 necessary steps for the correct implementation of the methodology:
31
32
33
34
35

- 36 **1- Identification of the Problem and Motivation** - define the research problem, highlighting
37 the importance of finding a solution.
- 38 **2- Definition of Objectives** - Elaborate research objectives, taking into consideration their
39 feasibility. Objectives can be of quantitative or qualitative nature.
- 40 **3- Design and Development** - Creation of the artefact, its desired functions, and architecture.
- 41 **4- Demonstration** - in an appropriate activity that solves one or more instances.
- 42 **5- Evaluation** - testing the artefact's effectiveness by measuring and comparing the achieved
43 and proposed objectives.
- 44 **6- Communication** - essential conveying all the necessary information about the problem
45 underlying its significance, explaining how the developed artefact aids in solving the proposed
46 problem and underlying its effectiveness to relevant audiences.
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55

56 It is important to understand that these steps suggest a problem- and objective-oriented iterative
57 process to design and develop a solution following the above nominal process sequence [18].
58
59
60

4. Research Design

This section includes a short explanation of the research objectives, how MACBETH helps achieve results, and a final explanation of the research proposal.

4.1 Research Objectives

This research lies in a twofold approach to tackling the intricate problem of fake news. Firstly, we seek to uncover and define the crucial criteria that guide the selection of countermeasures against the spread of FN. Grasping these criteria is paramount for crafting effective alternatives to combat FN-related crime. One such strategy is developing an MCDA-based framework for strategic decision-making when dealing with high-stakes FN. Another strategy is to provide recommendations for effectively tackling disinformation-related crime based on an MCDA analysis, thus laying the foundation for more focused and efficient countermeasures.

4.2 Utilising MACBETH

MACBETH, which stands for *Measuring Attractiveness by a Categorical Based Evaluation Technique*, is a decision analysis methodology commonly used in MCDA that considers multiple criteria or factors for evaluating and comparing different alternatives[19].

This method is designed to aid stakeholders in making decisions in situations where there are conflicting criteria preferences. Its objective is to provide a structured and systematic approach for evaluating and ranking alternatives using a categorical ranking system to assess the relative importance of the criteria and the performance of alternatives. The assignment of the DM qualitative descriptors (e.g., very weak, weak, moderate, strong, very strong) aids in expressing their preferences [17].

Another important aspect of this method is that it helps with modelling the preferences and values of DM by comparing criteria pairwise. A comparison of criteria allows for a derivation in a numerical scale for each criterion using a mathematical operation to convert qualitative preferences into numerical values, therefore allowing for the quantification of subjective judgments consistently.

This methodology incorporates consistency checks, ensuring the DM preferences are logical and contradictions-free. This way allows for the flagging of inconsistencies and their consequent review. Once the preferences for the criteria and alternatives are established, they are aggregated, thus generating an overall ranking or score for each alternative[17], [19]. In summary, MACBETH is a

useful method that offers a structured and transparent process for evaluating and comparing alternatives that incorporate subjective judgments and preferences.

4.3 Research Proposal

Considering the effective rise of crime related to **FN**, which has spiked in the digital era [2], an innovative and strategic approach is necessary to mitigate risk and its impact. Traditional methods have proven insufficient in selecting the appropriate course of action, and therefore, a comprehensive framework that considers the various criteria for a swift decision-making process for tackling crime is required. MCDA offers a systematic and structured approach that enables the DM to weigh multiple factors when selecting countermeasures against high-stakes crimes related to **FNs**.

This research defines the DM as an LEA responsible for tackling crime within a community of the European Union. It proposes the usages of MCDA, specifically utilising the Macbeth approach to set a framework for making evident the most suitable ranking of countermeasures to tackle a crime associated with **FNs** in the proposed LEA community. The ranking should be organised from the preferred countermeasure to the least preferred one.

By correctly applying the multi-criteria framework, utilising the M-Macbeth tool, and considering an agreeable set of criteria, a value tree will rank the best countermeasures based on the decision-maker's predefined set of alternatives. A value model will be built using the M-Macbeth tool. This multiple-criteria decision support system works through a qualitative judgement selecting the differences of value, aiding in the decision-making of a particular LEA. Figure 1 presents a schematic model summarising the product of the research.

Figure 1. Illustration of the Research Proposal

5. Demonstration

To demonstrate the execution of the proposed decision model, a decision was made to consult an LEA expert from the prestigious forensic investigation unit within the Swedish Police to act as a DM. This individual is responsible for spearheading efforts to combat the rising issue of **FN** that threatens

1
2
3 to impact the community. Working in an LEA tasked with developing and implementing effective
4 strategies that aid in counteracting the spread of Fake News and safeguarding the public trust.
5
6

7 The subsequent sub-sections will structure the model by selecting criteria and options, showing the
8 performance of the options, and presenting the additive model using M-MACBETH and its
9 application.
10
11
12

13 **5.1 Selection of Criteria**

14 The first step in structuring the model was the selection of the appropriate criteria in line with the
15 decision-maker's expertise and opinion. The following five criteria were selected:
16
17

- 18 • Criteria 1 – **Impact** refers to the effects or consequences of fake news, varying depending on the nature
19 of the content and the audience it reaches.
- 20 • Criteria 2 – **Context** identifies the circumstances, events, or background information surrounding a
21 particular story or report of fake news. It aids in assessing the credibility, reliability, and accuracy of
22 information.
- 23 • Criteria 3 - **Type of Event** refers to the type of incident related to fake news, which can be of different
24 types, e.g., misinformation, disinformation, clickbait, spam, untrustworthy propaganda, etc.
- 25 • Criteria 4 - **The Spread of Fake News** refers to the factors or things that help and lead to the spreading
26 of false information.
- 27 • Criteria 5 - **Probability** - the likelihood that a specific piece of information or news story is false or
28 inaccurate is known as the likelihood of fake news. It is frequently based on factors such as the source's
29 credibility, the evidence and sources used to support the claim, and biases or misinformation.
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40

41 Following the criteria selection, a descriptor was assigned to every criterion as follows:
42

- 43 • **Impact**: Descriptor quantitative, direct, and continuous.
- 44 • **Context**: Descriptor qualitative, constructed, and discrete.
- 45 • **Type of Event**: Descriptor qualitative, constructed, and discrete.
- 46 • **Spread of Fake News**: Descriptor qualitative, constructed, and discrete.
- 47 • **Probability**: Descriptor quantitative, direct, and continuous.
48
49
50
51
52

53 **5.2 Selection of the Options or Alternatives**

54 When questioned about what would be the best options to tackle fake news and mitigate its associated
55 risk, the DM mentioned the following five options:
56
57
58
59

- 60 • Educational Program(s),

- Direct Communication with the Agent(s) of Disinformation,
- Broad Communication with the Public,
- Ban the Source(s) of Disinformation,
- Investing in Moderation Software Tools.

The DM was then asked to select one option as the most preferred and another as the least preferred one.

5.2.1 Performance of the Options

To build the performance of the options, the DM was requested to characterise two reference levels (good and neutral) for each of the evaluation criteria. Since there may be situations where one option is better than all the others in a particular criterion, determining reference levels aids in determining whether the options are appealing. The reference levels of each criterion can be found in Tables 1 to 4.

Table 1. Reference Level of Criteria 1 (Impact) and 5 (Probability)

Reference Level	Criteria 1 (Impact)	Criteria 5 (Probability)
Good	85%	70%
Neutral	60%	40%

From criteria 2 to 4, the reference levels were established by constructing a qualitative descriptor that considers the preference-dependent attribute and the degree to which (impact range) the DM classifies each of them.

Table 2. Reference Level of Criteria 2 (Context)

Impact Level	Description	Reference Level
C1	Irrelevant context	
C2	Context with a low risk for the community	
C3	Context with an acceptable level of risk	Neutral
C4	Context with a high level of risk	Good
C5	Context with an extreme level of risk	

Table 3. Reference Level of Criteria 3 (Type of Event)

Impact Level	Description	Reference Level
1	Event with no identification in the community	
2	Event with a low degree of threat(s)	Neutral
3	Event with a noticeable degree of threat(s)	Good
4	Event with a great degree of threat(s)	
5	Event with a severe degree of threat(s)	

Table 4. Reference Level of Criteria 4 (Spread of the Fake News)

Impact Level	Description	Reference Level
L1	No spreading of fake news	
L2	Low spreading of fake news	
L3	Considerable levels of spreading of fake news	Neutral
L4	High level of spreading of fake news	Good
L5	Viral dissemination of fake news	

Once the reference level for each criterion was determined, it was possible to identify the performance profile of the options as presented in the following table.

Table 5. Performance Profile of the Options

Options	C 1 Impact	C2 Context	C3 Type of Event	C4 Spread of the Fake News	C5 Probability
Educational Program(s)	30%	C2	2	L2	40%
Direct Communication with Agent(s) of Disinformation	50%	C4	3	L3	70%
Broad Communication with the Public	80%	C3	4	L3	50%
Ban the Source(s) of Disinformation	40%	C5	5	L5	30%
Investing in Moderation Software Tools	20%	C3	3	L3	70%

5.3 Additive Evaluation Model Using the MACBETH

The model was structured, using the performance profile of the options, criteria and the two reference levels (good and neutral); an additive value model was constructed using the M-Macbeth software tool. The following value tree (Figure 2) was generated:

Figure 2. Value Tree

5.3.1 Value Functions

A value function was created to determine the scores of each option in each criterion. This function compares the performance levels in each criterion that was previously set. Depending on each criterion, performance levels can be either qualitative or quantitative. Scores will be generated from these performance values using a value function.

After defining the performance scales for each criterion, the DM was asked to verbally judge the differences in attractiveness between each level in the corresponding performance scales for each criterion using the MACBETH semantic scale as answers (these differences can be categorised as null, very weak, weak, moderate, strong, very strong, extreme, or any combination of these). Value functions were produced for each criterion.

The scale of scores, the DM responses concerning the variations in attractiveness, and the value functions for each criterion are shown below.

	85	80	60	50	40	30	20	Current scale
85		no	strong	v. strong	v. strong	v. strong	vstrg-extr	100
80			no	strong	strong	strong	v. strong	50
60				no	moderate	moderate	moderate	0
50					no	weak	moderate	-20
40						no	weak	-30
30							vweak-weak	-40
20								-45

Consistent judgements

Figure 3. Differences in attractiveness between the performance of the options on the Criteria 1 (Impact)

Figure 4. Value Function for the Criteria 1 (Impact)

	C5	C4	C3	C2	Current scale	
C5	no	vstrg-extr	v. strong	vstrg-extr	225	extreme
C4		no	strong	v. strong	100	v. strong
C3			no	weak-mod	0	strong
C2				no	-50	moderate
						weak
						very weak
						no

Consistent judgements

Figure 5. Differences in attractiveness between the performance of the options on the Criteria 2 (Context)

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Figure 6. Value Function (Numerical scale related to performance levels)

Type of Event						
	5	4	3	2	Current scale	
5	no	strong	v. strong	vstrg-extr	366.67	extreme
4		no	strong	strg-vstr	233.33	v. strong
3			no	moderate	100.00	strong
2				no	0.00	moderate
Consistent judgements						weak
						very weak
						no

Figure 7. Differences in attractiveness between the performance of the options on the criteria 3 (Type of Event)

Figure 8. Value Function (Numerical scale related to performance levels)

	L5	L4	L3	L2	Current scale	
L5	no	v. strong	v. strong	vstrg-extr	225	extreme
L4		no	strong	strg-vstr	100	v. strong
L3			no	moderate	0	strong
L2				no	-75	moderate
Consistent judgements						weak
						very weak
						no

Figure 9. Differences in attractiveness between the performance of the options on the Criteria 4 (Spread of the Fake News)

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Figure 10. Value Function (Numerical scale related to performance levels)

	70	50	40	30	Current scale	
70	no	strong	strong	strong	100.00	extreme
50		no	weak-mod	moderate	33.33	v. strong
40			no	very weak	0.00	strong
30				no	-16.67	moderate
Consistent judgements						weak
						very weak
						no

Figure 11. Differences in attractiveness between the performance of the options on the Criteria 5 (Probability)

Figure 12. Value Function for the Criteria 5 (Probability)

It is important to note that the M-MacBeth software tool offers a scale of scores, with the lower one receiving a score of 0 and the higher one receiving a score of 100, following the references earlier specified in the attributes of each criterion. This scale displayed by the software can be changed should the DM find one disagreeable criterion, per his opinion.

Except for the Impact value function, the DM agreed with all the other four value functions (*Context, Type of Events, Spread of the Fake News and Probability*). For the Impact criteria, the DM requested that the performance of the option "Direct Communication with Agent(s) of Disinformation (DCA)" be modified from 50 to 65. Changes that resulted in the scale are shown and referenced in Figures 12 and 13.

	85	80	65	60	40	30	20	Current scale
85	no	strong	v. strong	v. strong	v. strong	v. strong	vstrg-extr	100.00
80		no	strong	strong	strong	strong	v. strong	57.14
65			no	moderate	weak-mod	moderate	moderate	14.29
60				no	moderate	moderate	moderate	0.00
40					no	weak	weak	-14.29
30						no	vweak-weak	-21.43
20							no	-25.00

Figure 13. Differences in attractiveness between the performance of the options

Figure 14. Value Function for Criteria 1 (Impact) with new DCAD of 65%

5.3.2 Weighting Coefficients

After the DM provided his judgment about the difference in attractiveness between the performance profile of the options in each criterion, the DM was then asked to rank the difference in overall attractiveness between the criteria. Simple weighting was used after introducing the judgments in the decision-maker's position, in descending order (from left to right) of attractiveness. With reference levels for each criterion, it was possible to compare the level of attractiveness between the swings of each criterion. The DM approved the weights calculated for each criterion, with no changes having been made.

	[Cnt]	[Imp]	[PBB]	[SFN]	[TE]	[tudo inf.]	Current scale	
[Cnt]	no	weak	weak-mod	mod-strg	mod-strg	strong	31.82	extreme
[Imp]		no	weak	moderate	strong	strong	27.27	v. strong
[PBB]			no	moderate	strong	mod-strg	22.73	strong
[SFN]				no	strong	mod-strg	15.91	moderate
[TE]					no	vweak-weak	2.27	weak
[tudo inf.]						no	0.00	very weak
								no

Consistent judgements

Figure 15. Matrix of attractiveness judgments regarding the difference in global criteria.

Figure 16. The scale of the weights obtained for each criterion.

5.4 Application of the Additive Model

Using the additive value model in the M-MacBeth software, we could evaluate the attractiveness of each alternative after developing our model. As a result, the program uses the additive model to determine the overall scores for each option.

5.4.1 Computation of the Global Attractiveness of Each Option

The scores of each option in each criterion and the overall score are determined using the M-MacBeth software. The attractiveness values of the options are then determined using our additive model's value functions, criteria weights, and performance profiles.

Options	Overall	Imp	Cnt	TE	SFN	PBB
EP	-33.69	-21.43	-50.00	0.00	-75.00	0.00
DCAD	60.72	14.29	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00
BCP	28.45	57.14	0.00	233.33	0.00	33.33
BSD	108.03	-14.29	225.00	366.67	225.00	-16.67
IMST	18.18	-25.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00
[tudo sup.]	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
[tudo inf.]	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Weights :		0.2727	0.3182	0.0227	0.1591	0.2273

Figure 17. Option scores according to the Additive Model

Figure 18. Option Overall Thermometer

The BSD (Ban the Source of Disinformation) option is the most appealing one, according to the results of Figures 17 and 18 above.

6. Evaluation

To evaluate the decision model, the authors used a sensitive and robustness analysis. The sensitive analysis aims to understand the impact of uncertainties or fluctuations in the input variables of our model of decision. On the other hand, a robustness analysis refers to an examination of the stability and reliability of the decision-making model under various conditions and uncertainties; the goal is to assess how well the chosen options perform when faced with changes in criteria weights, variations in the input data or other sources of uncertainty [20].

6.1 Sensitive Analysis

Though the DM established the weights allocated to each option, he has the right to change them if unsure how to evaluate the criteria weights. As a result, it is possible to analyse the degree to which the model's recommendations vary when the weight of criteria is modified (while keeping the proportionality relationship between the other weights) by performing a sensitivity analysis on the weight of criteria. By analysing the sensitivity to each of the criteria's weights, we may evaluate the situations in which the most attractive option changes. To visualise the results of the sensitive analysis for each criterion, please consult the appendix of this article.

A sensitivity analysis demonstrated that a relatively insignificant change of 22.27% in a particular parameter substantially alters the relative attractiveness of alternative options, particularly emphasising DCAD's competitive edge over BSD. This narrow range of variation highlights the delicate balance between these two choices, suggesting that a slight adjustment within this range could elevate DCAD to parity with or even surpass BSD in terms of attractiveness.

6.2 Robustness Analysis

There is always uncertainty and imprecision in decision-making practices and modelling to select options, making it difficult to determine whether the most attractive options are robust. Robustness analysis should determine if an option remains the most attractive despite changes in option performance and criteria weight. It is a crucial aspect of MCDA, evaluating the sensitivity of outcomes and uncertainties in input data, model assumptions, and DM preferences. By identifying influential factors, robustness analysis enhances decision-making confidence and validates MCDA results, ensuring their stability across scenarios [21].

In other words, the global attractiveness rankings for each option differ if the option performs poorly on the criteria or changes the criteria weights.

To perform this analysis, the authors use M-Macbeth's robustness analysis feature. This feature introduced uncertainty in the performance and criteria weighting options in the local and global information sections.

First, as shown in Figure 41, the BSD option is recommended and robust without introducing any uncertainties into our model.

Figure 19. Robustness Analysis

In the figure above, additive dominance is present. Of this additive dominance, we see that the BSD option additively dominates all the other options. Option EP is dominated by all other options (additively dominated by BSD and IMST) and dominated by DCAD and BCP in all criteria. In consultation with the DM, the following degrees of uncertainty were considered in the analysis: Uncertainty of 10% for criteria impact, Uncertainty of 5% for criteria probability.

Figure 20. Robustness Analysis after inserting uncertainty in the performance of the options.

With the introduction of uncertainty in the performance profile of the options, of 10% in the impact criteria and 5% in the criteria probability, the BSD option remains the most attractive and continues to dominate all other options additively except in the case of "superior = all up". Respectively, the EP option continues to be dominated by all choices.

The same happens when we only insert uncertainty in the criteria weights (global information section), as shown in Figure 43, where with 7% uncertainty in the weights, the BSD option remains the option to recommend, nevertheless not being a robust choice in this scenario considering that the option does not dominate when all are upper (todo superior).

Figure 21: Robustness Analysis after inserting uncertainty in the criteria weights.

7. Recommendations to the Decision-Maker

The study's results and analysis conclude that BSD (Ban the Source of Disinformation) is the most attractive option and is, therefore, recommended to the decision-maker (DM). However, choosing the best option can be subjective due to the weight assigned to each criterion and uncertainties about how different options perform.

The sensitivity analysis reveals how changing the weight of specific criteria can shift the most attractive option away from BSD:

- **Impact Criteria:** Increasing its weight by 38.33% would make BCP (Broad Communication with the Public) more attractive than BSD.
- **Context Criteria:** A significant weight increase of 68.18% would make BCP and IMST (Investing in Moderating Software Tools) more attractive than BSD.

- **Type of Event Criteria:** A substantial increase of 97.73% in weight would make DCAD (Direct Communication with the Agent of Disinformation) and IMST more appealing than BSD.
- **Spread of Fake News Criteria:** An 84.09% increase in its weight would make IMST, BCP, and DCAD equally attractive as BSD.
- **Probability Criteria:** A minor increase of 22.27% in weight would make DCAD more attractive than BSD.

This analysis underscores the DM's significant role in the final decision. While substantial changes in the criteria weights are necessary for BSD to lose its status as the most attractive option, the DM's priorities and risk mitigation goals, particularly regarding FNs-crime, will ultimately guide his choice.

During the robustness analysis, BSD remained the best option under all three tested scenarios, even when accounting for uncertainty in the options' performance and criteria weights. DCAD consistently ranked as the second-best option.

In conclusion, the role of the analysts is to provide recommendations based on the study's results and analysis. However, the final decision on the most appropriate option, whether it's BSD or an alternative like DCAD, rests with the DM and their assessment of the risks involved.

8. Practical Implication and Lessons Learned

In accordance with the suggested research proposal the main objective of this work was to build a decision-model that aids LEAs and their communities to tackle disinformation and fake news in the area that they operate.

Researchers took upon the Macbeth method with the aid of M- Macbeth tool and the assistance of the DM to build an additive model demonstrating its utility in suggesting countermeasures to tackle crime taking into consideration both the DM expertise in the field and the community in which he operates – Sweden.

The execution of the proposed endeavour required frequent interview meetings with the DM to establish a valid criterion, options, and value tree and to build an additive model. The analysts used a qualitative approach to query the DM about making sure his preferences in tackling crime were carefully consider. At the same time, an effort was made to avoid common bias mistakes through the

1
2
3 incorporation of diverse perspectives when querying, as well as, in promoting critical reflection
4 throughout the elicitation process.
5
6

7 Furthermore, to evaluate the decision model, a sensitive analysis assessing how variations in input
8 parameters, specifically in the criteria weight, impacted the outcome of the developed decision model.
9 The analysis indicated a minor adjustment in a specific parameter could significantly change the
10 perceived desirability of an alternative option – BSD.
11
12
13

14
15 To further evaluate in terms of model robustness another analysis was conducted introducing
16 uncertainty in the performance of the alternatives, specifically 10% in the impact criteria and 5% in
17 the criteria probability and still BSD was the most dominant option, thus demonstrating the robustness
18 of the proposed model.
19
20
21

22
23 This research elucidates the utility of MCDA as a ground-breaking method to select countermeasures
24 through a socio-technical approach indicating that when faced with uncertainty it is possible to apply
25 a model of decision to carefully ponder the best course of action that takes in consideration a
26 multitude of factors and different criteria.
27
28
29

30
31 It is crucial to comprehend that, ultimately this is an approach that requires constant interaction with
32 the DM, and while this research underscores the transformative potential of MCDA in selecting
33 countermeasures through a socio-technical lens, it is crucial to acknowledge its inherent need for
34 continuous interaction with the DM. A balances approach taking advantage of a comprehensive
35 systematic approach of MCDA with the need for expeditious decision-making remains a critical
36 consideration in optimising the utility of MCDA in a real-world scenario.
37
38
39
40

41 42 43 **9. Conclusion** 44

45 This research offered the invaluable opportunity to engage as facilitators and implement a multi-
46 criteria analysis strategy, employing the MACBETH method to solve a practical problem – the
47 selection of countermeasures for high or extremely high-risk events related with fake news.
48 Throughout seven meetings, the interactions with the DM revealed a socio-technical approach that
49 showcased proficiency. The several interactions happened through teleconference sessions proved
50 instrumental as we utilised targeted questions to facilitate decision-making and simultaneously avoid
51 bias. Moreover, the authors were able to incorporate a firm evaluation of multi-criteria model to
52 conduct a sensitive and robust analysis that aided in having a solid decision model.
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 Lastly, decision-maker's reaction to the proposed result did not conform to the anticipated outcome.
4
5 The model outcome can predominantly be ascribed to the principle that a LEA would exclusively
6
7 contemplate the adoption of banning a source of fake news when the peril connected to disinformation
8
9 presents a substantial threat to the community. Fundamentally, the decision-maker operating LEA
10
11 was improbable to incorporate this alternative into their routine operations due to many factors,
12
13 encompassing potential legal ramifications and the perceived jeopardy to the principle of freedom of
14
15 expression. Furthermore, we underscored that the application of this option should be reserved solely
16
17 for mitigating a high-risk threat, warranting cautious consideration.

18 **9.1 Limitations**

19
20 The main difficulty throughout this process was decision-maker's unfamiliarity with the technical
21
22 vocabulary and facilitator's difficulty in explaining technical concepts throughout the teleconference
23
24 sessions.

25
26
27 **Another difficulty to this research work had to do with its initial ambition to build a decision**
28
29 **model applicable to any European Union community.** Nevertheless, the model was built from the
30
31 perspective of one DM, only one LEA, which may prejudice the outcome. Given the scope of the
32
33 model's applicability, it would be of the utmost importance to continue the developed research where
34
35 the same techniques are applied, considering a multitude of stakeholders from the EU having them as
36
37 decision-makers.

38 **9.2 Future Research**

39
40 Future research should apply decision methods to consider other LEAs' perspectives. Firstly,
41
42 understanding what countermeasures the scientific community suggests for tackling high-stakes FNs
43
44 would be of the utmost value. This could be achieved through a systematic literature review on the
45
46 subject. Secondly, should the involvement of multiple stakeholders be possible, it would be crucial
47
48 to confirm the suggested alternatives for mitigating risk through a DELPHI study initiative. **Also,** on
49
50 a smaller scale, a conference of decisions could also be used to validate a consensual criterion
51
52 throughout the EU.

53
54 **Lastly, future work could incorporate additional factors that may influence the DM, such as**
55
56 **legal, social, and ethical considerations. Moreover, to enhance practical applications, further**
57
58 **research could explore real-world case studies, integrate dynamic criteria weights, and develop**
59
60

1
2
3 **adaptive models that respond to evolving disinformation threats, thus providing a more**
4 **comprehensive decision-making tool.**
5
6

7 **Acknowledgements**

8
9
10 This work has been partially supported by the Europe Union's HE researches and innovation program
11 FERMI under the grant agreement No. 101073980 and INOV - Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas
12 e Computadores Inovação.
13
14

15 **Ethical Approval**

16
17
18 This study was conducted according to the Europe Commission's ethical guidelines and was reviewed
19 by the INOV's Research Program Ethical Committee, ensuring that all human participant procedures
20 complied with relevant regulations and ethical standards.
21
22
23

24 **Inform Consent**

25
26
27 All participants in this study provided informed consent before participation. They were fully briefed
28 on the study's objectives, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Participants were informed of their
29 right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. Consent was obtained,
30 ensuring that participants understood and agreed to the terms of their involvement.
31
32
33

34 **Supplementary Data**

35
36
37 Access to the M-Macbeth files is available upon request.
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

References

- [1] A. R. Dennis, D. F. Galletta, and J. Webster, 'Fake News on the Internet | Enhanced Reader', *Journal of Management Informations Systems*, vol. 38, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1080/07421222.2021.1990609.
- [2] P. N. Petratos, 'Misinformation, disinformation, and fake news: Cyber risks to business', *Bus Horiz*, vol. 64, no. 6, pp. 763–774, 2021, [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2021.07.012>
- [3] European Commission, 'Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions', Brussels, Apr. 2018. Accessed: Jan. 09, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52018DC0236>
- [4] '2018 Code of Practice on Disinformation | Shaping Europe's digital future'. Accessed: Jan. 09, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/2018-code-practice-disinformation>
- [5] S. Committee, 'Disinformation and "fake news": Final Report Eighth Report of Session 2017-19', Feb. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201719/cmselect/cmcmds/1791/1791.pdf>
- [6] J. Posetti and A. Matthews, 'A short guide to the history of "fake news" and disinformation a learning module for journalists and journalism educators', *International Center for Journalists*, vol. 7, 2018, doi: 10.1207/S15327728JMME1502_3.
- [7] E. Huber, B. Pospisil, and W. Haidegger, 'Modus Operandi in Fake News : Invited Paper', 2021, *IEEE*. doi: 10.1109/CogSIMA51574.2021.9475926.
- [8] International Organization for Standardization, 'ISO 31000 - Risk management - Guidelines', Geneva, 2018. [Online]. Available: www.iso.org
- [9] R. M. Stulz, 'Rethinking Risk Management', in *Corporate Risk Management*, Columbia University Press, 2016, ch. 5, pp. 87–120. doi: 10.7312/CHEW14362-005/HTML.
- [10] J. Varela da Costa, S. Bogeia Gomes, and M. Mira da Silva, 'Fake News: a conceptual model for risk management', *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications 2024 11:1*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 1–11, May 2024, doi: 10.1057/s41599-024-03096-0.
- [11] E. M. Aswad, 'In a World of "Fake News," What's a Social Media Platform to Do?', *Utah Law Rev*, no. 4, pp. 1009–1028, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.26054/0D-TGXD-4V9T>.
- [12] C. C. Ferreira, J. Robertson, and M. Kirsten, 'The truth (as I see it): philosophical considerations influencing a typology of fake news.', *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 150–158, 2020, doi: 10.1108/JPBM-12-2018-2149.
- [13] Z. Bastick, 'Would you notice if fake news changed your behavior? An experiment on the unconscious effects of disinformation.', *Comput Human Behav*, vol. 116, p. N.PAG-N.PAG, 2021, [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2020.106633>
- [14] T. S. Valerie Belton, *Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis: An Integrated Approach*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [15] C. A. Bana e Costa, T. G. Fernandes, and P. V.D. Correia, 'Prioritisation of public investments in social infrastructures using multicriteria value analysis and decision conferencing: a case study', *International Transactions in Operational Research*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 279–297, Jul. 2006, doi: 10.1111/J.1475-3995.2006.00549.X.
- [16] K. Marsh *et al.*, 'Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis for Health Care Decision Making—Emerging Good Practices: Report 2 of the ISPOR MCDA Emerging Good Practices Task Force', *Value in Health*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 125–137, Mar. 2016, doi: 10.1016/J.JVAL.2015.12.016.

- 1
2
3 [17] C. A. Bana e Costa and M. P. Chagas, 'A career choice problem: An example of how to use
4 MACBETH to build a quantitative value model based on qualitative value judgments', *Eur J*
5 *Oper Res*, vol. 153, no. 2, pp. 323–331, Mar. 2004, doi: 10.1016/S0377-2217(03)00155-3.
6
7 [18] A. Hevner and S. Chatterjee, *Design Science Research in Information Systems*. Boston:
8 Springer, 2010. doi: 10.1007/978-1-4419-5653-8_2.
9
10 [19] C. A. Bana e Costa and J. C. Vansnick, 'MACBETH — An interactive path towards the
11 construction of cardinal value functions', *International Transactions in Operational Research*,
12 vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 489–500, Oct. 1994, doi: 10.1016/0969-6016(94)90010-8.
13
14 [20] I. Dimitrakopoulos and K. Karamanis, 'Decision Making Using Multicriteria Analysis: A Case
15 Study of Decision Modeling Career in Education', *Case Studies in Business and Management*,
16 vol. 4, no. 2, p. 24, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.5296/CSBM.V4I2.11355.
17
18 [21] C.-L. Hwang and A. S. Md. Masud, 'Multiple Objective Decision Making — Methods and
19 Applications', vol. 164, 1979, doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-45511-7.
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Appendix

INDEX

- I. SENSITIVE ANALYSIS FOR THE CRITERIA 1 – IMPACTII
- II. SENSITIVE ANALYSIS FOR THE CRITERIA 2 – CONTEXTIV
- III. SENSITIVE ANALYSIS FOR THE CRITERIA 3 – TYPE OF EVENT\VI
- IV. SENSITIVE ANALYSIS FOR THE CRITERIA 4 – SPREAD OF THE FAKE NEWSVIII
- V. SENSITIVE ANALYSIS FOR THE CRITERIA 5 – PROBABILITYX

I. Sensitive Analysis for the Criteria 1 – Impact

Figures 22- 27 display the sensitivity analysis results concerning the weight of the impact criteria (Imp).

Figure 22. Sensitivity analysis on the weight of the criteria impact

Figure 23: Sensitivity analysis of the weight of the criteria impact for the BCP and BSD options

Figure 24. Sensitivity analysis to the weight of the criteria impact for the BCP and DCAD options

Figure 25. Sensitivity analysis to the weight of the criteria impact for the BSD and DCAD options

Figure 26. Sensitivity analysis to the weight of the criteria impact for the EP and IMST options

Figure 27. Sensitivity analysis to the weight of the criteria impact for the BCP and IMST options

The sensitivity analysis of the weight of criteria 1 (impact) from figures 22 to 27 revealed:

Weight of impact criteria < (below) 16.9% IMST is more attractive overall than BCP,

Weight of impact criteria = 16.9%: BCP and IMST are equally attractive,

Weight of impact criteria > (above) 16.9%: BCP is more attractive overall than IMST.

Weight of impact criteria < (below) 58.5% DCAD is more attractive overall than BCP,

Weight of impact criteria = 58.5%: DCAD and BCP are equally attractive,

Weight of impact criteria > (above) 58.5%: BCP is more attractive overall than DCAD.

Weight of impact criteria < (below) 65.6% BSD is more attractive overall than BCP,

Weight of impact criteria = 65.6%: BCP and BSD are equally attractive,

Weight of impact criteria > (above) 65.6%: BCP is more attractive overall than BSD.

Weight of impact criteria < (below) 72.6% BSD is more attractive overall than DCAD,

Weight of impact criteria = 72.6%: BSD and DCAD are equally attractive,

Weight of impact criteria > (above) 72.6%: DCAD is more attractive overall than BSD.

Weight of impact criteria < (below) 95.3% IMST is more attractive overall than EP,

Weight of impact criteria = 95.3%: IMST and EP are equally attractive,

Weight of impact criteria > (above) 95.3%: EP is more attractive overall than IMST.

General conclusion:

0 < weight of impact criteria < 65.6 %: BSD is more attractive overall,

Weight of impact = 65.6%: BSD and BCP are equally attractive,

Weight of impact > 65.6%: BCP is more attractive overall,

Weight of impact = 72.6%: BSD and DCAD are equally attractive,

Weight of impact > 72.6%: DCAD is more attractive,

Weight of impact = 95.3%: EP and IMST are equally attractive,

Weight of impact > 95.3%: EP is more attractive.

II. Sensitive Analysis for the Criteria 2 – Context

Figures 24- 26 a sensitivity analysis results regarding the weight of the context criteria (Cnt).

Figure 28. Sensitivity analysis on the weight of the criteria context

Figure 29. Sensitivity analysis to the weight of the criteria context for the BCP and DCAD options

Figure 30. Sensitivity analysis to the weight of the criteria context for the BCP and IMST options

The sensitivity analysis of the weight of the criteria 2 (context) from figures 28 to 30 revealed the following results:

Weight of context criteria < (below) 9.3%: BCP is more attractive overall than DCAD,

Weight of context criteria = 9.3%: BCP and DCAD are equally attractive,

Weight of context criteria > (above) 9.3%: DCAD is more attractive overall than BCP.

Weight of context criteria < (below) 100%: BCP is more attractive overall than IMST,

Weight of context criteria = 100%: BCP and IMST are equally attractive.

General conclusion:

0 < weight of context criteria < 100%: BSD is more attractive overall,

Weight of context criteria = 100%: BCP and IMST are equally attractive.

From the sensitivity analysis above, only a variation of 68.18% (from 31.82 to 100%) in the weight of context criteria will make another option (in this case, BCP and IMST) become as attractive as BSD.

III. Sensitive Analysis for the Criteria 3 – Type of Event\

In the sensitivity analysis referring to the weight of criteria type of event (TE), we obtained the results expressed in figures 31, 32 and 33.

Figure 31. Sensitivity analysis on the weight of the criteria type of event

Figure 32. Sensitivity analysis to the weight of the criteria type of event for the DCAD and IMST options

Figure 33. Sensitivity analysis to the weight of the criteria type of event for the BCP and DCAD options

The sensitivity analysis of the weight of the criteria 3 (type of event) from Figures 27 to 29 revealed the following results:

Weight of type of event criteria < (below) 21.3%: DCAD is more attractive overall than BCP,

Weight of type of event criteria = 21.3%: BCP and DCAD are equally attractive,

Weight of type of event criteria > (above) 21.3%: BCP is more attractive overall than DCAD.

Weight of type of event criteria < (below) 100%: DCAD is more attractive overall than IMST,

Weight of type of event criteria = 100%: DCAD and IMST are equally attractive.

General conclusion:

0 < weight of type of event criteria < 100%: BSD is more attractive overall,

Weight of type of event criteria = 100%: DCAD and IMST are equally attractive.

From the sensitivity analysis above, a high variation of 97.73% (from 2.27 to 100%) in the weight of the type of event criteria will make another option (in this case, DCAD and IMST) become attractive as BSD.

IV. Sensitive Analysis for the Criteria 4 – Spread of the Fake News

In the sensitivity analysis referring to the weight of criteria spread of the fake news (SFN), we obtained the results expressed in figures 30, 31, 32 and 33.

Figure 30: Sensitivity analysis on the weight of the criteria spread of the fake news

Figure 31: Sensitivity analysis of the weight of the criteria SFN for the BCP and DCAD options

Figure 32: Sensitivity analysis of the weight of the criteria SFN for the IMST and DCAD options

Figure 33: Sensitivity analysis to the weight of the criteria spread of the fake news for the IMST and BCP options

The sensitivity analysis of the weight of criteria 4 (spread of the fake news) from figures 30 to 33 revealed the following results:

Weight of spread of the fake news criteria < (below) 100%: BSD is more attractive overall,

Weight of spread of the fake news criteria = 100%: BCP, DCAD and IMST are equally attractive.

General conclusion:

0 < weight of spread of the fake news criteria < 100%: BSD is more attractive overall,

Weight of spread of the fake news = 100%: DCAD, BCP and IMST are equally attractive.

From the sensitivity analysis only with an extreme variation of 84.09%, from 15.91% to 100%, in the weight of the spread of the fake news criteria, would the IMST, BCP and DCAD options be equally attractive as BSD.

V. Sensitive Analysis for the Criteria 5 – Probability

In the sensitivity analysis referring to the weight of criteria probability (PBB), we obtained the results expressed in figures 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39 and 40.

Figure 34: Sensitivity analysis on the weight of the criteria probability

Figure 35: Sensitive Analysis of the weight of the criteria probability for the BSD and DCAD

Figure 36: Sensitivity analysis to the weight of the criteria probability for the IMST and DCAD

Figure 37: Sensitivity analysis to the weight of the criteria probability for the BSD and BCP

Figure 38: Sensitivity analysis to the weight of the criteria probability for the IMST and BCP

Figure 39: Sensitivity analysis to the weight of the criteria probability for the EP and BSD

Figure 40: Sensitivity analysis to the weight of the criteria probability for the IMST and BSD

The sensitivity analysis of the weight of the criteria 5 (probability) from figures 34 to 40 revealed the following results:

Weight of probability criteria < (below) 33%: BCP is more attractive overall than IMST,

Weight of probability criteria = 33%: BCP and IMST are equally attractive,

Weight of probability criteria > (above) 33%: IMST is more attractive overall than BCP.

Weight of probability criteria < (below) 45%: BSD is more attractive overall than DCAD,

Weight of probability criteria = 45%: DCAD and BSD are equally attractive,

Weight of probability criteria > (above) 45%: DCAD is more attractive overall than BSD.

1
2
3 Weight of probability criteria < (below) 56.3%: BSD is more attractive overall than IMST,
4

5 Weight of probability criteria = 56.3%: IMST and BSD are equally attractive,
6

7 Weight of probability criteria > (above) 56.3%: IMST is more attractive overall than BSD.
8

9 Weight of probability criteria < (below) 70.2%: BSD is more attractive overall than BCP,
10

11 Weight of probability criteria = 70.2%: BCP and BSD are equally attractive,
12

13 Weight of probability criteria > (above) 70.2%: BCP is more attractive overall than BSD.
14

15 Weight of probability criteria < (below) 91.9%: BSD is more attractive overall than EP,
16

17 Weight of probability criteria = 91.9%: EP and BSD are equally attractive,
18

19 Weight of probability criteria > (above) 91.9%: EP is more attractive overall than BSD.
20

21 **General conclusion:** 22 23

24 $0 < \text{weight of probability criteria} < 45\%$: BSD is more attractive overall,
25

26 Weight of probability criteria = 45%: BSD and DCAD are equally attractive,
27

28 Weight of probability criteria > 56.3%: IMST is more attractive overall,
29

30 Weight of probability criteria > 70.2%: BCP is more attractive,
31

32 Weight of probability criteria > 91.9%: EP is more attractive,
33

34 Weight of probability criteria = 100%: DCAD and IMST are equally attractive.
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

João Varela da Costa
INOV INESC
Rua Alves Redol, 9
1000-029, Lisboa
Portugal
T: +351 92 407 92 16
E: joao.v.costa@inov.pt

24th of September 2024

Prof. Jenifer Winter
Editorial Office
Journal of Information, Communication & Ethics in Society

Re: ID JICES-07-2024-0089 (Journal of Information, Communication & Ethics in Society) –
Decision on Manuscript.

Dear Prof. Jenifer Winter,

I am delighted to present the revised manuscript "*Using MCDA To Select Countermeasures Against Fake News*". I want to express my profound gratitude to the reviewers for their invaluable feedback and suggestions, which have been instrumental in enhancing our final work.

We have incorporated all the reviewers' feedback and made the necessary revisions to address their concerns.

As a result, I am resubmitting the manuscript for your review. Your insights are highly valued. I have included a marked-up PDF version of the manuscript. Please refer to table below, where I have comprehensively responded to each reviewer's comment.

Once again, I want to express my sincere appreciation for the reviewers' meticulous review and insightful comments, which have significantly contributed to the quality of our manuscript.

Thanks.

Regards,

João Varela da Costa

Corresponding Author
Researcher | PhD Candidate

Reviewer #1	
Comment	Action
This is a timely and much-needed study. The topics are interesting and intriguing for readers.	The authors thank the reviewer for recognising the value of our contribution.
However, the writing lacks clarity. In some cases, the reader has to predict the possible meaning of the terms used. The terms fake news and disinformation may have been used interchangeably. Which changes the context in places.	The word "disinformation" has been removed from the abstract. In the first paragraph of the introduction, the authors clearly defined fake news and disinformation, highlighting the differences between the two concepts. The authors have diligently combed through the entire text to ensure the accurate usage of "disinformation" in line with the provided reference.
One example is the research objectives. It states at the beginning that the twofold approach is to tackle the problem of fake news, but later in the paragraph, it states disinformation.	The authors have ensured the proper term was used in the research objectives.
I highly suggest the authors to define fake news and disinformation clearly. Several articles have been able to differentiate them in a much better way. One example: Dennis, A. R., Galletta, D. F., & Webster, J. (2021). Fake news on the internet. <i>Journal of Management Information Systems</i> , 38(4), 893-897. But several other articles define the concepts much well.	The first paragraph of the introduction now defines Fake News and Disinformation and explains the difference between the two concepts. The suggested reference is now cited in the paper.
Overall, the writing in many sections, including especially introduction and research background, needs to provide a clear storyline for the readers.	The introduction and research background sections were rewritten for a more straightforward storyline.
The methodology seems robust but the explanations of the results needs clarity for the readers. The article is publishable by making the necessary changes.	The results section was rewritten to enhance clarity for the reader.
Reviewer #2	
Comment	Action
I highly suggest the authors to define fake news and disinformation clearly.	The first paragraph of the introduction has been revised to provide clear definitions of fake news and disinformation, while also highlighting the distinctions between the two concepts.
Reviewer #3	
Comment	Action
Appreciate the detailed study, could be expanded more for robustness keeping other factors that may impact the DM and develop further for more practical applications.	We acknowledged this limitation in the conclusion section and are already working on increasing its robustness as part of our future research.
Associated Editor	
Comment	Action
As far as overall content of the article, these are minor revisions. However, concerns about readability, missing references, etc. mean that the paper needs to be heavily edited to ensure readability, definition of key terms, etc. Please check that each reference cited in text is in the references section and vice-versa.	The authors took the time to carefully review the introduction, research background, and other sections of the paper to ensure readability. The references mentioned in the text were verified against the references section, and vice versa.